

CURE MONITORING OF CARBON/EPOXY COMPOSITE BY OPTICAL-FIBER-BASED DISTRIBUTED STRAIN/TEMPERATURE SENSING

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1 Introduction

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) have high specific strength and stiffness and have been used extensively in many industrial fields. Especially in a field of aircraft, their application extends to primary structures. Therefore, quality assurance of the composite materials is necessary and effective cure monitoring techniques of composite materials are becoming more and more important since quality of the materials is very dependent on their cure processes.

There are several cure monitoring techniques utilized for composite materials, such as differential scanning calorimetry [1], dielectrometry [2] and point type optical fiber sensors which include extrinsic Fabry-Perot type sensors [3,4], Raman spectroscopy [5] and fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensor [6]. Among these techniques, optical fiber sensors are very useful for strain and temperature monitoring of composite materials. Since they are light weight and small, they do not affect mechanical properties of the materials in which sensors are embedded. Recently, pulse-pre-pump Brillouin optical time domain analysis (PPP-BOTDA) [7] was developed. This system can measure strain or temperature distribution along an optical fiber using Brillouin peak frequency shifts caused by strain and temperature changes. However, since both strain and temperature changes induce a shift of Brillouin peak frequency, PPP-BOTDA system cannot separate strain and temperature contributions from measured frequency shifts.

In order to overcome this limitation, a newly developed hybrid Brillouin-Rayleigh system [8] is considered to be quite useful. The technique utilizes two independent phenomena in an optical fiber, Brillouin and Rayleigh scatterings, and can separately measure strain and temperature distribution along the optical fiber. This study

demonstrates a new effective cure monitoring technique by applying this hybrid system to composite materials (Figure 1). First, the strain and temperature coefficients of Brillouin and Rayleigh scatterings were determined by tensile tests at constant temperature and temperature tests in strain-free condition. Secondly, using the determined coefficients, strain and temperature measurement of a CFRP laminate on which an optical fiber was attached was performed in tensile tests at different temperatures. Finally, an optical fiber for the hybrid system, an FBG sensor and a thermocouple were embedded in a CFRP laminate to measure thermal residual strain and temperature change in the cooling down period of the cure process. The proposed monitoring technique was verified by comparing the measured results.

Fig. 1. Cure monitoring technique of composite materials by hybrid Brillouin-Rayleigh system

2 Measurement Principles

The hybrid Brillouin-Rayleigh system consists of a measuring optical fiber, a PPP-BOTDA subsystem and a high-resolution Rayleigh scattering spectrum

(RSS) [9] subsystem. Each subsystem provides measured shifts for Brillouin and Rayleigh scatterings, denoted by $\Delta\nu_B$ and $\Delta\nu_R$, when applied strain and temperature change. Each value is a function of both applied strain and temperature. In the hybrid system, combination of measured $\Delta\nu_B$ and $\Delta\nu_R$ is used to separate strain and temperature changes with the following set of equations:

$$\Delta\nu_B = C_1\Delta\varepsilon + C_2\Delta T \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta\nu_R = D_1\Delta\varepsilon + D_2\Delta T \quad (2)$$

In these equations, $\Delta\varepsilon$ and ΔT are strain and temperature changes, and C_1 and C_2 are the strain and temperature coefficients for Brillouin scattering. In the same way, D_1 and D_2 are the strain and temperature coefficients for Rayleigh scattering. These coefficient values were determined by experiments in the following section.

3 Measurement of Strain/Temperature Coefficients

3.1 Strain Coefficients

The strain coefficients for Brillouin and Rayleigh scatterings were measured by tensile tests of a CFRP laminate on which a measuring optical fiber was attached. The optical fiber was Heatop 300 supplied by Totoku Electric Co., ltd. The material of the specimen was T800S/3900-2B supplied by Toray Industries, Inc. Stacking configuration was $[0_{16}]$. The specimen was cured in an autoclave. The optical fiber was then bonded on the surface of the specimen by an epoxy type adhesive. Both strain gauges and thermocouples were also attached on the same surface. Tensile strains of 500, 1000, 1500 and 2000 $\mu\varepsilon$ were applied at room temperature and the frequency shifts of the both scatterings were measured at each strain condition. The specimen was maintained at constant temperature during the whole test. Figure 2 and 3 show the relationships between Brillouin/Rayleigh frequency shifts and the applied strain. In the both scatterings, the relationships were liner and the strain coefficients of Brillouin and Rayleigh scatterings (i.e., the gradients of the graphs) were determined to be $C_1=5.004\times 10^{-5}$ GHz/ $\mu\varepsilon$, $D_1=-1.525\times 10^{-1}$ GHz/ $\mu\varepsilon$ respectively.

Fig. 2. Relation between peak frequency of Brillouin scattering and applied strain.

Fig. 3. Relation between frequency shift of Rayleigh scattering and applied strain.

3.2 Temperature Coefficients

The temperature coefficients of Brillouin and Rayleigh scatterings were determined by temperature tests using a thermostatic chamber. Temperature in the chamber was increased from 20°C to 200°C in a step-by-step manner and frequency shifts were measured at each holding temperature. Figure 4 and 5 show the relationships between both frequency shifts and holding temperature. Again, the relationships were liner and the temperature coefficients of Brillouin and Rayleigh scatterings were determined to be $C_2=1.090\times 10^{-3}$ GHz/°C, $D_2=-1.498$ GHz/°C respectively. All the determined coefficients are listed in Table 1.

Fig. 4. Relation between peak frequency of Brillouin scattering and temperature.

Fig. 5. Relation between frequency shift of Rayleigh scattering and temperature.

Table 1. Coefficients in Eq. (1) and (2)

coefficient	value	unit
C_1	5.004×10^{-5}	GHz/ $\mu\epsilon$
C_2	1.090×10^{-3}	GHz/ $^{\circ}\text{C}$
D_1	-1.525×10^{-1}	GHz/ $\mu\epsilon$
D_2	-1.498	GHz/ $^{\circ}\text{C}$

4. Tensile Test of Composite at Different Temperatures

4.1 Experimental Method

The separated strain and temperature measurement by the hybrid system were verified by tensile tests of a CFRP laminate at different temperatures. The specimen was the same as the one used for determining the strain coefficients. Figure 6 shows an illustration of the specimen with attached sensors.

A measuring optical fiber for the hybrid system, strain gauges and thermocouples were attached on the surface of the specimen. First, frequency shifts of Brillouin and Rayleigh scatterings were measured at 500, 1000, 1500 and 2000 $\mu\epsilon$ strain conditions at room temperature (23 $^{\circ}\text{C}$). Subsequently, the specimen was unloaded to 0 $\mu\epsilon$ and heated to 53 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ by an infrared heater. After the temperature was maintained at constant value (53 $^{\circ}\text{C}$), tensile strains of 500, 1000, 1500 and 2000 $\mu\epsilon$ were again applied and frequency shifts were measured.

Fig. 6. Schematic diagram of specimen and sensors for tensile test.

4.2 Result and Discussion

Figure 7 and 8 show the frequency shifts at the different temperatures. In the both scatterings, contributions of applied strain to each frequency shifts were expressed as gradients of the graphs and contribution of temperature change was clearly separated and expressed as gaps in y axis. Using Eq. (1), (2) and the coefficients in Table 1, strain and temperature were calculated separately from the measured frequency shifts. Table 2 compares the calculated strain and temperature with the values obtained by the strain gauges and the thermocouples. The values of the hybrid system agreed well with the ones of the other sensors, confirming that the hybrid system can accurately measure strain and temperature of CFRP laminate with a single optical fiber.

Fig. 7. Relation between peak frequency of Brillouin scattering and applied strain.

Fig. 8. Relation between frequency shift of Rayleigh scattering and applied strain.

Table 2. Calculated temperature changes ΔT and residual strain $\Delta\epsilon$.

Strain gauges and thermocouples		The hybrid Brillouin-Rayleigh system	
$\Delta\epsilon$ ($\mu\epsilon$)	ΔT ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	$\Delta\epsilon$ ($\mu\epsilon$)	ΔT ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
469	0	520	-3
935	0	974	-2
1408	0	1449	-2
1857	0	1879	-1
357	31	510	31
832	31	982	32
1305	31	1447	32
1776	31	1907	32

5. Cure Monitoring of Composite

5.1 Experimental Method

An optical fiber for the hybrid Brillouin-Rayleigh system was embedded in a CFRP laminate to measure thermal residual strain and temperature change in cooling down period of the cure process. An FBG sensor and a thermocouple were also embedded for comparison. Figure 9 shows an illustration of the specimen indicating location of the optical fibers and the thermocouple. Material of the specimen was T800S/3900-2B and stacking configuration was $[90_{16}]$. All the sensors were embedded between 8th ply and 9th ply. The specimen was cured in an autoclave, and the applied pressure was 0.5 MPa.

5.2 Result and Discussion

Figure 10 shows temperature history in the cure process. Peak frequencies of Brillouin scattering were measured at holding temperature (153.4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) and room temperature (26.5 $^{\circ}\text{C}$). Meanwhile, frequency shifts of Rayleigh scattering were measured at each holding temperature and the total frequency shift was calculated by summing each frequency shifts. Figure 11 and 12 show the distributions of Brillouin peak frequencies and representative Rayleigh frequency shift. In these graphs, x axis expresses distance of measuring points along optical fiber. The part of 24.4 ~ 24.7 m corresponds to the embedded area. Distributions of the measured frequencies were almost uniform in the specimen. All the values of Rayleigh scattering were listed in Table 3. By using these results, the total frequency shifts of Brillouin and Rayleigh scatterings were determined to be -0.32 GHz and 713.4 GHz respectively. Substituting these values to Eq. (1) and (2), temperature change and residual strain were calculated and compared with the values of the FBG sensor and the thermocouple in Table 4. By the hybrid system, temperature decrease and compressive strain due to thermal shrinkage of the laminate could be separately measured and the values agreed well with the ones obtained by the FBG sensor and the thermocouple, confirming the feasibility of the proposed effective cure monitoring system. A little difference between these results could be due to viscoelastic property of epoxy matrix at high temperature.

Fig. 9. Schematic diagram of specimen with embedded optical fiber sensors and thermocouple.

Fig. 10. Temperature history measured by thermocouple.

Fig. 11. Peak frequencies of Brillouin scattering at 153.4 °C and 26.5 °C.

Fig. 12. Frequency shift of Rayleigh scattering when temperature changed from 79.5 °C to 70.9 °C.

Table 3. Frequency shifts of Rayleigh scattering Δv_R at each temperature.

T (°C)	Δv_R (GHz)	T (°C)	Δv_R (GHz)
153.4	-	88.0	49.0
146.0	59.6	79.5	45.3
137.5	54.3	70.9	45.2
129.8	45.2	62.4	44.8
121.5	46.5	53.9	44.5
113.2	45.4	45.2	45.5
104.3	45.0	36.5	47.7
96.6	44.7	26.5	50.8

Table 4. Calculated temperature difference ΔT and residual strain $\Delta \epsilon$.

	The hybrid Brillouin-Rayleigh system	FBG sensor and thermocouple
ΔT (°C)	-142.9	-126.9
$\Delta \epsilon$ ($\mu\epsilon$)	-3274	-3569

6. Conclusions

This study demonstrated the new effective cure monitoring technique by applying the hybrid Brillouin-Rayleigh system to composite materials. First, the strain and temperature coefficients were determined by the tensile tests and the temperature tests. Using these coefficients, strain and temperature measurement of the CFRP laminate on which an optical fiber was attached was performed by the tensile tests at different temperatures. The

results of the hybrid system agreed well with the results obtained by the other sensors. Finally, an optical fiber for the hybrid Brillouin-Rayleigh system was embedded in the CFRP laminate to measure thermal residual strain and temperature change in cooling down period of the cure process. By the hybrid system, temperature decrease and compressive strain due to thermal shrinkage of the CFRP laminate could be separately measured and the values agreed well with the ones obtained by the other sensors. These results verified the proposed technique is quite useful for cure monitoring of composite materials. By applying the technique to actual manufacturing of composite products, quality assurance of large-scale composite can be effectively accomplished.

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